

DYNAMIC RESPONSE AND FAILURE OF COMPOSITE AND SANDWICH STRUCTURES UNDER FLUID STRUCTURE INTERACTION

Y. W. Kwon*, R. D. McCrillis

Dept. of Mechanical & Aerospace Engineering, Naval Postgraduate School, Monterey, USA

* Corresponding author (ywkwon@nps.edu)

Keywords: *laminated composites, sandwich structures, fluid-structure interaction, impact,*

1 Introduction

The effect of hydrodynamic mass is very significant to composite and sandwich structures under dynamic loading as material densities of composites are very comparable to the water density. In order to evaluate the effect of the Fluid-Structure Interaction (FSI) on dynamic responses and failure modes of laminated composite and sandwich structures, low velocity impact testing was conducted for those structures [1-3]. In particular, the testing was undertaken when the structures were submerged in water (i.e., called wet structure) or in dry air (i.e., called dry structure). Comparison of the test results obtained either under water or in air with the same impact condition provided the effect of FSI on the laminated composite and sandwich structures. To this end, an impact testing machine was developed to provide the same impact condition in both water and air, respectively. Furthermore, care was taken to prevent the effect of moisture on the laminated composite and sandwich structures.

2 Experiments

2.1 Fabrication of Test Samples

Flat panels were constructed of laminated or sandwich composites, respectively, for testing. The composite materials were carbon/vinyl-ester and e-glass/vinyl-ester, respectively while balsa was used for the core material of the sandwich structure. The Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding (VARTM) technique was used for the fabrication process. The laminated composite specimens were made of eight layers of plain woven fabrics while the sandwich composites had three composite layers for each skin and a 6.35 mm thick core.

For plate specimens, the tested section was 304.8 mm x 304.8 mm while that for the beam specimens

was 304.8 mm x 25.4 mm. Because both plate and beam specimens were clamped along the boundary, the actual sizes of the test specimens were bigger than the test sectional areas. The strain gages were attached to the specimens on the opposite surface of the impact side. Also, all specimens to be tested under water were sealed properly to prevent any water penetration while not altering the composite specimen's material properties.

2.2 Impact Testing

Impact tests were conducted using a specially designed drop weight testing system thoroughly described in Refs. [2-3], that consisted of a drop weight impactor, load transducer, strain gages, high speed data analyzer. The C-clamps were used to facilitate clamped boundary conditions. Impact force and strains as a function of time were recorded for transient motion of the sample.

For testing, the impact tower was lowered into an anechoic water tank that was filled with water, so that the samples were submerged below the water surface. Dry testing took place with the tower in the same position, but with the water drained out of the tank in order to maintain similar testing conditions.

Figure 1 shows the impact testing machine partially submerged into an anechoic water tank. In order to provide the same impact condition to both air and water impact cases, the impact machine was designed such that the impacting object had no contact with the water because this would disturb the still water. Instead, an impact rod was placed between the impacting object and the composite specimen to be tested. The impact rod is partially submerged with a very small distance away from the specimen. As the impacting object hit one end of the impact rod, the rod moves slightly to strike the composite specimen. As a result, the perturbation to

still water caused by the impact rod becomes very minor.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Laminated Composites

The first series of tests performed to laminated carbon composite plates did not have structural damage so that the FSI effect could be evaluated directly. Figure 2 shows the comparison of the impact forces between the dry and wet impacts under the impact condition of 12 Kg impactor at the height of 1.07 m. As shown in the figure, the wet impact results in a much higher peak force than the dry impact under the same impact condition. This is due to the added mass effect with FSI. With the added mass, the composite plate behaves like a denser plate so that it moves much slowly compared to the dry plate. As a result, the contact force between the impact rod and the plate becomes higher.

The time history of strain responses were also compared between the dry and wet impact cases. Figure 3 compares the strains at the quarter point along a diagonal direction of the plate. Because of the larger impact force, the strain under the wet impact is greater than that under the dry impact. Also, it is evident that there is a major difference in the dynamic response frequency between the two impact cases. The added mass effect reduces the frequency significantly. The first lowest frequency of the dry impact response is approximately three times larger than that of the wet impact response.

Figure 4 shows the strain responses at the one-eighth location along the diagonal and close to the corner of the plate. The figure suggests that the FSI effect is very important for the strain at that position. In other words, the FSI effect is much greater at a location closer to the clamped boundary.

The next impact test was conducted with a lower drop height with 0.71 m. The impact force-time histories are plotted in Fig. 5. As Fig. 5 is compared to Fig. 2, the lower drop height yields a less impact force as expected. However, the peak impact forces have almost the same magnitude between the dry and wet impact cases. The comparison of strains at the quarter location of the diagonal is provided in Fig. 6. Even though the difference in magnitudes of strains between dry and wet impact cases is reduced

with the lower impact height, the change of the response frequency remains almost the same.

3.2 Sandwich Composites

The next tested samples were sandwich composite beams made of e-glass/vinyl-ester skins and balsa core. For these specimens, impact testing was conducted progressively by increasing the impact height incrementally with a constant impact mass. The low impact height was selected to prevent damage in the specimens. However, as the impact height increased, damage was observed in the specimens.

Table 1 compares the peak impact forces between the dry and wet impacts on sandwich composites. The results show that before damage occurs, the wet impact produces a higher peak impact force than the dry impact as observed in the laminated composite panels. Therefore, damage occurs at a lower impact height for the submerged specimens.

Furthermore, impact heights were selected to create damage in both dry and wet cases using a single impact, and their resulting impact forces are compared in Table 2. Under the same impact condition, the peak impact force is slightly greater for the dry impact when there is damage in the specimens. This may be explained as below. While the wet impact has an earlier damage initiation than the dry impact because of the added mass effect, the damaged specimen loses its stiffness. Hence, the final peak force with the wet impact becomes lower than that with the dry impact after damage.

The wet impact also affected the damage location. The dry impact failure occurred at the clamped boundary location while the wet impact yielded failure at the impact site. Even though the sandwich composites are made of balsa core which may have somehow non-uniform properties, the statistical data clearly suggests the trend. Five wet samples out of seven failed at the impact site while five dry specimens out of six failed at the clamped site. Figure 7 shows the strain history for a wet impact. The strain drop at the centerline due to failure was followed immediately by the strain reduction at the boundary.

DYNAMIC RESPONSE AND FAILURE OF COMPOSITE AND SANDWICH STRUCTURES UNDER FLUID

4 Conclusions

Impact testing was undertaken for both laminated and sandwich composite specimens while they were in air or in water, respectively. Because the density of the water is very comparable to the density of the composite specimen, the added mass effect from FSI is significant. As a result, the peak impact force was greater for the wet impact than for the dry impact under the same impact condition when there was no damage in the specimens. Because of the higher impact force, the wet impact resulted in failure initiation at a lower drop height than the dry impact. However, once damage occurred, the impact peak force was slightly greater for the dry impact. The wet impact also had a different failure location for sandwich beam specimens. Dry sandwich beams failed at the clamped site while wet specimens failed at the impact site (i.e. at the center of the specimen).

Fig.1. Impact testing machine submerged into anechoic water tank

Table 1. Peak Impact Forces Resulting from Progressive Impact Testing

	Drop Height (mm)			
	406.4	457.2	609.6	660.4
Wet Test #1	869	885*	-	-
Wet Test #2	1030	1090*	-	-
Avg. Wet test	950	988		
Dry Test #1	767	792	1032*	
Dry Test #2	892	905	990	1010*
Avg. Dry Test	830	849	1011	1010

* indicates failure initiation of the sample.

Table 1. Failure Impact Forces from Single Impact Testing

Impact Type	Drop Height (mm)	Force (N)
Wet Impact	660.4	1006
Dry Impact	660.4	1032

Fig.2. Comparison of impact forces between dry and wet impact cases at drop height 1.07 m

Fig.3. Comparison of strain-time histories at the quarter point along the diagonal of the plate between dry and wet impact cases at drop height 1.07 m

Fig.4. Comparison of strain-time histories at the 1/8th point along the diagonal of the plate between dry and wet impact cases at drop height 1.07 m

Fig.5. Comparison of impact forces between dry and wet impact cases at drop height 0.71 m

Fig.6. Comparison of strain-time histories at the quarter point along the diagonal of the plate between dry and wet impact cases at drop height 0.71 m

(a) Wet specimen

Dry specimen

Fig.7. Comparison of failure locations between wet and dry impact

Fig.8. Impact force and strain responses for submerged sandwich impact (center failure from 457.2 mm drop)

References

- [1] Y. W. Kwon, "Study of Fluid Effects on Dynamics of Composite Structures", *ASME Journal of Pressure Vessel Technology*, Vol. 133, June 2011, 031301-6.
- [2] Y. W. Kwon, A. C. Owens, A. S. Kwon, and J. M. Didoszak, "Experimental Study of Impact on Composite Plates with Fluid-Structure Interaction", *Int. Journal of Multiphysics*, Vol. 4, No. 3, 2010, pp. 259-271.
- [3] Y. W. Kwon and A. C. Owens, "Chapter 15. Dynamic Responses of Composite Structures with Fluid-Structure Interaction", *Advances in Composite Materials-Ecodesign and Analysis*, (ed. By B. Attaf), InTech, 2011